

EXISTENCE RESULT FOR INITIAL VALUE PROBLEM WITH NONLINEAR FUNCTIONAL RANDOM FRACTIONAL DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION

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ABSTRACT:- In this paper we prove the existence result for initial value problems with nonlinear functional random fractional differential equations under Caratheodory condition.

KEY WORDS:- Random fractional differential equation, fractional integral, Caputo fractional derivative etc.

2000 MATHEMATIC SUBJECT CLASSIFICATION:- 26A33, 47H10.

1. INTRODUCTION:-

The linear as well as nonlinear initial value problem of random differential equations have been studied in the literature by the authors since long time refer a Dhage[4-6]. Similarly the fraction differential equation are frequently use in many branches of engineering and science It has been mentioned first by Liouville in a paper from 1832. There are real world phenomena with anomalous dynamics such as signals transmission, network traffic and so on. In this case the theory of fractional differential equation is a good tool for modeling such as phenomena. For some fundamental result in the theory of fractional differential equations. We refer paper of Lakshmikantham [9, 10, 11] and [13,14].

Let \mathbb{R} denote the real line and Let $I_0 = [-r, 0]$ and $I = [0, T]$ be two closed and bounded interval in \mathbb{R} for some $r > 0$ and $T > 0$. Let $J = I_0 \cup I$. Let $C(I_0, \mathbb{R})$ denote the space of continuous \mathbb{R} valued function I_0 . We equip the space $C = C(I_0, \mathbb{R})$ with a supremum norm $\| \cdot \|_C$ defined by

$$\|x\|_C = \sup_{t \in I_0} |x(t)|$$

Clearly C is a Banach Space which is also a Banach Space with respect to this norm. For a given $t \in I$ define a continuous \mathbb{R} -valued function.

$$x_t: I_0 \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \text{ by } x_t(\theta) = (t + \theta), \theta \in I_0$$

Let (Ω, \mathcal{A}) be a measurable space i.e. a set Ω with a σ -algebra of subset of Ω and for given a measurable function $x: \Omega \rightarrow C(J, \mathbb{R})$.

Consider nonlinear functional random fractional differential equations of the form (in short RFDE)

$$\left. \begin{aligned} {}^C D^\alpha x(t, \omega) &= f(t, x_t(\omega), \omega) \text{ a.e } t \in J, 0 < \alpha < 1 \\ x(0, \omega) &= x_0(\omega) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1.1)$$

Where x is a random function; x_0 is random, $D^\alpha x$ is the Caputo fractional derivative of x with respect to the variable $t \in J$ and $f: J \times \mathbb{R} \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is given function.

2. EXISTENCE RESULT:-

Let E denote a Banach space with the norm $\| \cdot \|$ and let $Q: E \rightarrow E$. We further assume that the Banach space E is separable i.e. E has countable dense subset and let β_E be the σ - algebra of Borel subset of E . We say

a mapping $x: \Omega \rightarrow E$ is measurable if for any $B \in \beta_E$ one has

$$x^{-1}(B) = \{(\omega, x) \in \Omega \times E : x(\omega, x) \in B\} \in \mathcal{A} \times \beta_E$$

Where $\mathcal{A} \times \beta_E$ is the direct product of the σ -algebras \mathcal{A} and β_E those defined in Ω and E respectively.

Let $Q: \Omega \times E \rightarrow E$ be a mapping. Then Q is called a random operator if $Q(\omega, x)$ is measurable in ω for all $x \in E$ and it is expressed as $Q(\omega) x = Q(\omega, x)$. A random operator $Q(\omega)$ on E is called continuous (resp. compact, totally bounded and completely continuous) If $Q(\omega, x)$ is continuous (resp. compact, totally bounded and completely continuous) in x for all $\omega \in \Omega$.

Lemma 2.1[12]: Let $B_R(0)$ and $\overline{B_R}(0)$ be the open and closed ball centered at origin of radius R in the separable Banach space E and let $Q: \Omega \times \overline{B_R}(0) \rightarrow E$ be a compact and continuous random operator. Further suppose that there does not exists an $u \in E$ with $\|u\|=R$ such that $Q(\omega) u = \lambda u$ for all $\lambda \in \Omega$ where $\lambda > 1$. Then the random equation $Q(\omega)x = x$ has a random solution, i.e. there is a measurable function $\xi: \Omega \rightarrow \overline{B_R}(0)$ such that $Q(\omega)\xi(\omega) = \xi(\omega)$ for all $\omega \in \Omega$.

Lemma 2.2[12]: (Carathéodory) Let $Q: \Omega \times E \rightarrow E$ be a mapping such that $Q(\cdot, x)$ is measurable for all $x \in E$ and $Q(\omega, \cdot)$ is continuous for all $\omega \in \Omega$ Then the map $(\omega, x) \rightarrow Q(\omega, x)$ is jointly measurable.

We seek random solution of (1.1) in Banach space $C(J, \mathbb{R})$ of continuous real valued function defined on J . We equip the space $C(J, \mathbb{R})$ with the supremum norm $\| \cdot \|$ defined by

$$\|x\| = \sup_{t \in J} |x(t)|$$

It is known that the Banach space $C(J, \mathbb{R})$ is separable. By $L^1(J, \mathbb{R})$ we denote the space of Lebesgue measurable real-valued function defined on J . By $\| \cdot \|_{L^1}$ we denote the usual norm in $L^1(J, \mathbb{R})$ defined by

$$\|x\|_{L^1} = \int_0^1 |x(t)| dt.$$

We need the following definition in the sequel.

Definition 2.1: A Carathéodory function $f: J \times \mathbb{R} \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called random L^1 - Carathéodory if for each real number $r > 0$ there is a measurable and bounded function $h_r: \Omega \rightarrow L^1(J, \mathbb{R})$ such that

$$|f(t, x, \omega)| \leq h_r(t, \omega) \quad \text{a.e } t \in J.$$

Where $|x| \leq r$ and for all $\omega \in \Omega$

We consider the following set of hypothesis

H1) The function $(t, x) \rightarrow f(t, x, \omega)$ is continuous for a.e. $\omega \in \Omega$.

- H2) The function $\omega \rightarrow f(t, x, \omega)$ is measurable for a. e. $\omega \in \Omega$.
- H3) There exist $y \in \mathbb{R}$ s.t. $x_0(\omega) \in \overline{B_R}(0)$ for a. e. $\omega \in \Omega$ where
 $\overline{B_R}(0) = \{x \in \mathbb{R} : \|x - x_0\| \leq \varepsilon\}$.
- H4) There exist $K > 0$ and $x_0 \in \Omega$ s.t. $\|f(t, x, \omega)\| \leq \frac{K}{\Gamma\alpha}$
a.e. $\omega \in \Omega$. And Γ is a gamma function

Our main existence result is

Theorem 2.1: Assume that the hypothesis $H_1 - H_4$ hold. Suppose that there exist a real number $R > 0$ such that $R > r_1 \|\gamma(\omega)\|_{L^1} \psi(\mathbb{R}) \dots$ (2.1) for all $\omega \in \Omega$ where $r_1 = \max_{t \in [0,1]} r(t)$, $r(t)$ is in the greens function

Then the (1.1) has a random solution defined on J

Proof: - Set $E = C(J, \mathbb{R})$ and define a mapping $Q: \Omega \times E \rightarrow E$ by

$$Q(\omega)x(t) = x_0(\omega) + \int_0^t g_\alpha(t-s)f(s, x_s(\omega), \omega) ds \dots(2.2)$$

a.e. $\omega \in \Omega$ and for all $t \in J$. (Equation (2.2) is an Integral representation of (1.1)) Then the solution of (1.1) is fixed point of operator Q .

Define a closed ball $\overline{B_R}(0)$ in E centered at origin with radius R where the real number R satisfies the inequality (2.1). We show that Q satisfies all the condition of lemma 2.1 on $\overline{B_R}(0)$.

First we show that Q is random operator in $\overline{B_R}(0)$. Since $f(t, x_t(\omega), \omega)$ is random Caratheodory and $x(t, \omega)$ is measurable, the map $\omega \rightarrow f(t, x_t(\omega), \omega)$ is measurable. Similarly the product $g_\alpha(t-s)f(s, x_s(\omega), \omega)$ of continuous and measurable function is again measurable. Further the integral is a limit of finite sum of measurable function. Therefore the map

$$\Omega \rightarrow x_0(\omega) + \int_0^t g_\alpha(t-s)f(s, x_s(\omega), \omega) ds = Q(\omega)x(t)$$

is measurable.

As a result Q is random operator on $\Omega \times \overline{B_R}(0)$ in to E .

Next we show that the random operator $Q(\omega)$ is continuous on $\overline{B_R}(0)$. Let x_n be a sequence of point in $\overline{B_R}(0)$ converging to the point x in $\overline{B_R}(0)$. Then it is sufficient to prove that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q(\omega)x_n(t) = Q(\omega)x(t) \text{ for all } t \in J, \omega \in \Omega.$$

By the dominated convergent theorem we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q(\omega)x_n(t) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left[x_0(\omega) + \int_0^t g_\alpha(t-s) f(s, x_n(s), \omega) ds \right] \\ &= x_0(\omega) + \int_0^t g_\alpha(t-s) f(s, x_s(\omega), \omega) ds \\ &= Q(\omega)x(t) \end{aligned}$$

For all $t \in J, \omega \in \Omega$. This shows that $Q(\omega)$ is a continuous random operator on $\overline{B_R}(0)$.

Now we show that $Q(\omega)$ is a compact random operator on $\overline{B_R}(0)$.

To finish it, we should prove that $Q(\omega)(\overline{B_R}(0))$ is a uniformly bounded equi continuous set in E for each $\omega \in \Omega$. Since the map $\omega \rightarrow \frac{Ka^\alpha}{\Gamma\alpha+1} \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$.

Let $\omega \in \Omega$ be fixed then for any $x: \Omega \rightarrow \overline{B_R}(0)$ has

$$\begin{aligned} |Q(\omega)x_n(t) - x_0(\omega)| &\leq \int_0^t g_\alpha(t-s) |f(s, x_n(s), \omega)| ds \\ &\leq \frac{K}{\Gamma\alpha} \int_0^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} ds \\ &\leq \frac{Ka^\alpha}{\Gamma\alpha+1} \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \end{aligned}$$

Next we show that $Q(\omega)(\overline{B_R}(0))$ is equicontinuous set in E for any $x \in \overline{B_R}(0), t_1, t_2 \in J, \varepsilon > 0$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} |Q(\omega)x(t_1) - Q(\omega)x(t_2)| &\leq \frac{K}{\Gamma\alpha} \int_0^{t_2} (t_2 - \tau)^{\alpha-1} - \\ &\quad (t_1 - \tau)^{\alpha-1} d\tau + \frac{K}{\Gamma\alpha} \int_{t_2}^{t_1} (t_1 - \tau)^{\alpha-1} d\tau \\ &\leq \frac{2K}{\Gamma\alpha+1} (t - s)^\alpha < \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

Hence for all $t_1, t_2 \in J$

$$|Q(\omega)x(t_1) - Q(\omega)x(t_2)| \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } t_1 \rightarrow t_2 \text{ uniformly for all } x \in \overline{B_R}(0).$$

Therefore $Q(\omega)\overline{B_R}(0)$ is compact. Then we know it is compact by Arzela - Ascoli theorem for each $\omega \in \Omega$. Consequently $Q(\omega)$ is a completely continuous random operator on $\overline{B_R}(0)$.

Finally we suppose there exist such an element u in E with $\|u\| = R$ satisfying $Q(\omega)u(t) = \lambda u(t, \omega)$ for some $\omega \in \Omega$ and $\lambda > 1$. Now for this $\omega \in \Omega$ we have

$$\lambda u(t, \omega) = Q(\omega)u(t)$$

$$\begin{aligned} |u(t, \omega)| &\leq \frac{1}{\lambda} |Q(\omega)u(t)| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\lambda} |x_0(\omega) + \int_0^t g_\alpha(t-s)f(s, x_s(\omega), \omega) ds| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\lambda} x_0(\omega) + \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^t g_\alpha(t-s)f(s, x_s(\omega), \omega) ds \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\lambda} x_0(\omega) + \frac{ka^\alpha}{\lambda\Gamma\alpha+1} \\ &\leq \rho \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{For all } t \in J \text{ where } \rho = \frac{1}{\lambda} x_0(\omega) + \frac{ka^\alpha}{\lambda\Gamma\alpha+1}$$

This contradicts to inequality (2.1) this all the condition of lemma 2.1 are satisfied.

Hence random equation $Q(\omega)x(t) = x(t, \omega)$ has a random solution in $\overline{B_R}(0)$ i.e. there exist a measurable function $\xi: \Omega \rightarrow \overline{B_R}(0)$ such that $Q(\omega)\xi(t) = \xi(t)$ for all $\omega \in \Omega$ and $t \in J$. As a result RFDE (1.1) has a random solution defined on J . This completes the proof.

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